

SOME SCIENTIFIC VIEWS ABOUT CONSECUTIVE TRANSLATION

Nurillayeva Sevinch Nurmamatovna

(Scientific researcher of SamSIFL)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10401315>

Annotation. This article is devoted the specific features of consecutive translation. Oral translation is interlingual and intercultural mediation, which ensures that the addressee understands the maximum (or at least optimal) share of the total meaning inherent in the message by the sender. Interpreting is an activity carried out under stress, often at or near the limit of the interpreter's strength. Often, a consecutive interpreter has to deal with segments containing many hundreds of words and lasting several minutes.

Key words: memory, translator, information, short-term memory, source text, target text, speech.

The use of translation cursive allows you to relieve the translator's short-term memory, frees him from the eternal fear of forgetting the content of the material being translated, and also allows you to work with sections of text of significant length and complexity. Translation cursive writing is a special recording system that allows an interpreter "in real time" to record on paper a sufficient number of semantic elements of the source speaker's speech in order to form a sound translation text based on them [1, p. 37]. The main task of translation cursive writing is to create strongholds for instant retrieval from the memory of the translator of information that has already entered his brain through auditory receptors [2, p. 65].

The translation cursive written by the translator is formed at the analysis stage and read at the synthesis stage.

For the purposes of translation analysis, it is important to distinguish between the surface and semantic structure of a text. The surface of the text is a sequence of symbolic units that has the properties of coherence and integrity. Due to the limited capacity of short-term memory, a significant amount of text information cannot be remembered by the translator "directly," that is, at a superficial level. Trying to remember every word (to retain superficial forms in memory) leads to the loss of truly important information.

The only way to perceive, retain in memory and convey in translation the meaning of the original piece of text is the deepest possible semantic processing of the material, which inevitably involves a departure from superficial forms, structures and vocabulary. The goal is to reduce the redundancy of information (compression) without losing its essential elements and to create a system of semantic connections of various levels and types, ensuring the safety of the material during the period of synthesis and pronunciation of the translation segment of the text [1, p. 19]. Translation cursive writing as a tool of the translation analysis system involves working mainly at the level of the semantic structure of the text. The semantic structure of a text is the sum of the meanings of each segment of the text. By "meanings" we mean all the elements of semantics that are actualized in this specific context by the speaker.

What does the translation process look like from the translator's point of view? The translation process begins for the translator with listening to the speaker's speech, that is, listening (analysis stage). At the initial stage, the translator receives the entire set of information encoded at the "surface level" of the original text. The surface of the source text belongs to the source language. The perception of the "surface" of each segment of the original proceeds almost simultaneously with the semantic processing of its content, and the

separation of these processes, of course, is largely conditional. Even at the stage of perception of the original, the competent use of translation cursive gives the translator an additional opportunity to think more deeply about the semantic structure of the source text, record precise information, make some translation decisions, and prepare for constructing the translation text.

The key stage of the interpreting process, the success of which reveals the full professionalism of the translator or the lack thereof, is the stage of deverbalization (analysis stage). Semantic processing of the content of the source text occurs at the stage of deverbalization, when the meanings contained in the surface forms of the source text are released from their linguistic (verbal) shell [3, p. 65]. By perceiving and storing in memory or in recording the semantic content of speech, the translator is distracted from information about how exactly this content was expressed by the original author, that is, what words, expressions and syntactic constructions the author chose for this.

The semantic content of the text is diverse and multi-level. Meanings can be expressed lexically, morphologically, syntactically, prosodically. The translator must not so much select equivalents for each of the elements of the semantic content of the , but create in translation a text that adequately conveys the sum of the meanings of the original in its entirety [4, p. 18].

In the translator's notes, the main place will be given to recording information about what is said, that is, the deep semantic content of the text, and not its superficial design. The semantic structure of the text, freed as much as possible from the verbal shell, loses connection with the source language. It also does not belong to the translating language. Thus, the result of deverbalization should be a set of deep structures that unite referents and the most general information about predicative, tense, modal, register, emotional, evaluative, pragmatic and other parameters of the source text. It is at this stage of maximum compression of information and its separation from the source language (language in general) that it can be most usefully recorded on paper using a translation record. However, an effective recording system does not have to be cumbersome and burdensome.

The stage of deverbalization is followed by the stage of switching (code-switching, translation). This stage is unobservable and does not require conscious effort. From the moment this stage is passed, information begins to unfold.

At the reverbalization stage (synthesis stage), the translator transforms all perceived and stored information into syntactic, lexical, morphological, phonetic and other forms of the translating language. The automaticity of synthesis lies in the fact that the selection of lexical and grammatical units from the language into which the translation is being carried out (target language) is made in a minimum time based on previous units of speech (context). Automatic synthesis is not only knowledge of the equivalents of translation units, but also the ability to quickly find a close (approximate) match, i.e. analogue [2, p. 46]. For a translator who used cursive writing, this is the stage of reading his note. The deeper and more complete the deverbalization was carried out, the less during reverbalization the danger of literalism, "under-translations" (translatese). At the stage of reverbalization, the translator will act like any speaker, that is, he will look for numerous and non-repetitive ways to put these meanings into a linguistic shell, but in another language. The success of this operation will depend on the talent, experience and erudition of the translator, on the richness of his vocabulary and the breadth of his stylistic repertoire.

The process of oral translation is completed by voicing the final text. In fact, reverbalization and pronunciation of the final text occur almost simultaneously. At this stage, the result of the paradigmatic choice is transformed into a linear syntagmatic (“horizontal”) sequence, which is implemented in spoken speech. At this stage, the only important thing is that the translator can, without errors, hesitations and delays, read all possible information from his own notes and recall other elements of the content of the spoken text segment.

Translation cursive writing is by no means a recording of individual words and phrases; it is the skeleton of a message, which, at the moment of voicing, instantly acquires the flesh of full-fledged information and is saturated with the blood of logical connections [2, p. 70]. The development and widespread use of translation cursive increases the degree of translation adequacy by an order of magnitude.

References:

1. Зубанова И.В. Скоропись в последовательном переводе. Английский язык (с аудио- и видеоприложением). Москва: Р. Валент, 2013.
2. Красовский Д.И., Чужакин А.П. Конференц – перевод (теория и практика). 2-е издание, исправленное и дополненное. Москва: Р. Валент, 2015.
3. Миньяр-Белоручев Р.К. Записи в последовательном переводе. Москва: Проспект-АП, 1969.
4. Аликина Е.В. Переводческая семантография. Запись при устном переводе. Москва: АСТ: Восток-Запад, 2006.
5. Абсаматова Г. Б. LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF SIGN LANGUAGE AUTOMATIZATION //МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 3.
6. Bakhodirovna A. G. REQUIREMENTS FOR THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF AN INTERPRETER IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 27. – №. 2. – С. 71-74.
7. Nurmatovna N. S. PROBLEMS OF CREATING A MODEL OF THE INTERPRETATION PROCESS //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 27. – №. 2. – С. 75-78.
8. Daminov N. K., Nurullayeva S. N. THE FEATURES OF INTERPRETING AND IT’S USE //ВЕСТНИК МАГИСТРАТУРЫ. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 155.
9. Daminov N. K. SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION INTERPRETING AS A MODERN TYPE OF TRANSLATION //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 77-81.
10. Daminov N. Using some strategies in simultaneous interpreting process //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 381.
11. Abdimal B. THE IMPACT OF CHILDREN’S LITERATURE ON COGNITIVE AND EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT //Конференция: Союз Науки и Образования. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 2. – С. 46-50.
12. Abdimal o’g’li A. B. Leksik Birliklarning Lingvomadaniy Xususiyatlari (“Shum Bola” Asarining Tarjimasida Misolida) //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2023. – Т. 34. – С. 236-239.
13. Abdimal o’g’li A. B. FRAZEOLGIK BIRLIKLARNING LINGVOMADANIY XUSUSIYATLARI //IQRO. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 601-603.